

THE CONCEPT OF AGE IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Abduraimova is the daughter of Madinakhan Dilshodjon

Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10002697>

In the Uzbek people, time is like a flowing river. In the conceptual views of time, the concepts such as the fact that a person's life in this world is very short, that it is transient, and that he lives forever in the mortal world, that it is necessary to appreciate the time in this world and work for eternal life, are reflected. In Western culture, there are proverbs like time is money, time is more valuable than gold, but in Uzbek language, time is spoil, and time is loss; time erodes the mountain, water gnaws the rock; time-judge; There are sayings like you win from time and you win from happiness. It is probably from this that the appreciation of time and life in this world, and encouragement to use it productively, has become a tradition in the works of Uzbek philosophers and poets, as well as in Uzbek proverbs. Today, concepts with the meaning of time, such as time, date, age, year, life are easily understood, and the units representing these concepts form a separate system in the language.

One of these concepts is the concept of "age", which forms the concept of time. In the language, in particular, in Uzbek, the formation of lexical units meaning "young" has gone through a long historical process. The life of a person, the periods of this life are measured based on what, how the life span of a person or society is measured and what they are called, we do not always remember when we look at the dates on our mobile phones or when we are reminded of the birthdays of our friends every day on social networks. Our ancient ancestors determined the summation of time based on clearly observable natural phenomena. For example, the light part of the day is called day (sun). They had no concept of day before, usages such as I will come in two days, three days' journey are the effects of this view so far.

We know that the moon and its various appearances are also a unit of time. At the same time, in the Uzbek language, the time of a person's life since birth, each year of this period is called "yosh". It is known that in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, young homonyms are given as words. It contains two words meaning "tear" and "time, period" as cognates. It is known that Turkic peoples have been engaged in animal husbandry since ancient times. They started counting the year from the month of spring, that is, when the barra grass grew. After all, the basis for the summary of the year was the time when it was possible to graze cattle in nature, i.e., the time of migration with cattle to the mountains, hills, and latitudes. This was the time when grasses and lawns grew green. French scientist Louis Bazén's article entitled "Conception vozrasta u drevnih tyurkskih narodov", That is, the concept of age in ancient Turkic peoples, was published in 1986 in "Zarubejnaya Turkologiya" magazine. This article quotes the following passage from the "Annals of the Chu Dynasty", which ruled in China in 557-581: "They (that is, the Turkic peoples in the territory of Mongolia) determined the change of years and the summation of time by means of green grass." The barra grasses were named with the word "Yash". Later, the time when the grass was blue was used for the summation of the year, that is, this time and the period until its return were also called "yash". For a lamb born in spring, this spring is the first spring, and the second of the next spring, year 3 was counted as spring 3. Then the lamb that lived for 2 years was blind for 3 springs. That is, it was 3 years old. The word "live" used for green grass was the basis for the formation of the word green (color) depending on the color of the grass. On

the basis of vagility, the meaning developed in 2 directions, such as age, which means the water of the eyes, and age, which gives the meaning of time. This word yosh exists in many Turkic languages except Chuvash with various phonetic variations. For example, in Kyrgyz and Altai, it is called jash. Today, the development of the meanings of the word "yosh" in the form of tears and the age of a person has reached the level of homonymy.

Although the Turkic peoples later used units of measurement such as the Chinese Muchal calendar based on animal names, the Arab Hijri calendar, and the Gregorian calendar, still the fact that the beginning of the year coincides with spring is of conceptual importance. This can be seen through these proverbs: Early spring, late autumn. A good year is known from spring. The sorrow of the day is morning, the sorrow of the year is spring. So, although the word Navroz is borrowed from the Persian-Tajik language, the true essence of this holiday reflects the long history of our nation. In the Uzbek language, the concept of "age" means the level of physical and social development of a person over time. It is known that this development is determined by how long a person lives. In our language, as well as in many other languages, there are units that make up the concept of "age", such as childhood, adolescence, maturity (middle age), old age. These concepts have conceptual, value-based and figurative structures. We mentioned above that the conceptual organizer of the concept of age is almost the same in different languages. For example, the concept of childhood in all languages consists of young age, not having enough life skills and qualifications, cuteness, etc. But in some places, the boundaries of the conceptual structure of the "age" concept can be distinguished based on the way of life of the speakers. For example, as a result of early marriage in the Uzbek nation, the age limit is different compared to other nations. In our country, 40 years of age for marriage is the norm in Western countries.

In English, there are proverbs with the opposite meaning, such as "Life begins at forty". It can be seen from these examples that the issue of age limit can be different in different languages. The value-based organizers of the age concept are unique in each language. Here we will touch on the issue of the concept of "old age". It is known that the realization of the concept in language is analyzed mostly through idioms, proverbs and proverbs. We use the same method. In Uzbek, old age is treated as a special quality. The intention to reach this age is expressed, showing respect to the elderly is characteristic of the Uzbek national culture. The axiological view of old age is reflected in the following proverbs:

A house with an old man has a fairy; A child is a model of sweetness, an old man is a beggar of sweet words; When the young comes to work, when the old comes to eat; Respect of the young is a debt, respect of the old is a duty. In the Uzbek language, the wisdom of the elderly is reflected in the following proverbs: The hand of youth is strong, the mind of old age; Wisdom adorns old age, humility adorns youth. Elderly people have a lot of life experience reflected in the following proverbs: A house with an old person has a zari; A house with an old man has a fairy, a house with a fairy has a bar; The angel of the old house, Saranjomi, Sarishtasi; He has a lot of character. The fact that the elderly are worthy of attention and the issue of showing them proper respect is reflected in the following proverbs: Do not curse the elderly, do not hurt your young soul; Keep the belly in the palm, Keep the dead for a week. In the English language culture, old age as a value is not as strong as it is in ours, but it exists. For example, it can be seen in the following proverbs: older is wiser; The essence of age is intelligence; No one loves like an old man; Only an old man has the patience to plant a tree. It should be noted

that based on the mentality of the people, in our opinion, the view of old age as a value in English is a little weaker than that of Uzbeks. This can be seen through proverbs with positive and negative connotations of old age. In the scientific work of the Russian researcher T.A.Znamenskaya, 83 proverbs about old age in English were collected, and it was noted that 51 of them have a negative and 26 have a positive meaning. In relation to old age, the assessment of physical weakness in English is strong: Old people only walk in hospitals; A broken bell never sounds good; Old age is a testing phase; Old age is not a joy; Old age is not a blessing. A similar proverb can also be found in Russian: starost ne radost kabi. In French linguistic culture, we do not see old age as the owner of great experience: Years know more than books. The best wine comes from an old bottle. Very good music was played on the old violin. Old age is considered a special value in Japanese language culture. This can be seen through their following proverbs: Talk to an old man like your father, an old (Old) proverb does not deceive, an old (Old) river does not dry up. In conclusion, it can be said that the concept of "time" is a very broad issue, and it can be studied monographically. Such studies show that the Uzbek people's views, concepts, figurative thinking, conclusions and experiences about time are unique through the national spirit and language.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY